

IMPROVING THE TECHNICAL TRAINING OF GRECO-ROMAN Wrestlers

O'zbekiston Davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti,
Xalqaro kurash turlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati kafedrası o'qituvchilari
Abdikulov Jandos Nurjon o'g'li, Nigmatov Ibroxim Maxmud o'g'li,
Melimuratov Azizbek Xolmurod o'g'li

Abstract

The article describes how to optimize training techniques in wrestling. Techniques of modeling the teaching of technical techniques are studied in wrestling classes. We used a questionnaire on the use of training process modeling methods among trainers.

Key words: *physical training, technical methods, training, training, modeling, optimization*

YUNON-RIM KURASHCHILARINING TEXNIK TAYYORGARLIKLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Annotatsiya

Maqolada kurashda texnikani tayyorlashni qanday optimallashtirish mumkinligi tasvirlangan. Kurash darslarida texnik texnikani o'qitishni modellashtirish texnikasi o'rganiladi. Biz trenerlar orasida o'quv jarayonini modellashtirish usullaridan foydalanish bo'yicha so'rovnomadan foydalanildi.

Kalit so'zlar: *jismoniy tarbiya, texnik usullar, mashg'ulotlar, mashg'ulotlar, modellashtirish, optimallashtirish*

The issues of development and popularization of sports in our country are actively developing. In order to promote physical culture and sports, we can study the work done to organize and develop sports in foreign countries and adapt it to

the conditions of our country.

Effective management of the training process involves the use of various models. It is customary to understand a model as a sample (standard, standard) in a broader sense - any sample (mental or conditional) of one or another object, process or phenomenon. The development and use of models is associated with modeling - the process of building, studying and using models to determine and refine characteristics and optimize the process of sports training and participation in competitions. The terms "model", "modeling" deeply penetrated the theory and practice of sports. In periodic scientific and methodological publications on sports, these terms and their derivatives are currently found about 20 times more often than in the late 60s - early 70s of the XX century. This alone testifies to the fact that modeling as a scientific and practical method has spread widely in modern theory and practice of sports. The functions that models perform in solving the problems of the theory and practice of sports can be of a different nature. Firstly, models are used as a substitute for an object so that studies on the model will provide new information about the object itself. When experimenting with the model, it is possible to obtain new knowledge, which is a reflection of the structure and functions of the model. After checking the knowledge of the model from the point of view of their significance for the object, the obtained theoretical ideas can become an integral part of the theory of the object. Thus, the results of studies of the structure of muscle tissue in animals both under ordinary conditions and after intense training based on analogies between the structure of human and animal tissues were used to improve the theory of sports selection and orientation, the development of speed-strength qualities and endurance. The theoretical concepts obtained as a result of working with this model have been subjected to additional verification and refinement in the course of biopsy studies in humans in recent years. Secondly, models are used to generalize empirical knowledge, to comprehend the regular relationships of various processes and phenomena in the

field of sports. Empirical knowledge, processed in model representations and implemented in models, contributes to the creation of appropriate theoretical generalizations. [2.601]

Researchers (VI Kozlovsky et al., 1978) proposed a block model of player model characteristics. These are of three levels.

The first is the result of player and team action in team attacking or defending.

The second is technical equipment, special and tactical physical training and mental stability.

The third - characteristic of functional training, morphological features, age of sports experience.

Modeling involves learning or repeating some of the physical properties and phenomena of restoring forms such as scientific theoretical understanding. It is an exploration of the properties of objects (processes) with other objects that are their models. [4.80]

People have long been known as a modeling tool and have been uncertain in their work, and have compared this uncertainty to what is clearly apparent to them. Comparison of uncertainty to accuracy is an event of secondary displacement, in other words, that accuracy acts as a model of uncertainty. [3.184]

Objective of the study: To determine the role and effectiveness of modeling in the popularization of sports wrestling.

Research objectives: - Study of literature on modeling.

- To learn the value and effectiveness of sports modeling by asking a questionnaire among coaches.

This transfer of knowledge from one body to another in a certain relationship is called logical conclusions.

The modeling approach does not directly relate to the object under study, but rather by learning about model similarity. Thus, modeling is an intermediate chain

between the subject of knowledge and the object.

Currently, method modeling is seen as a "major weapon" in complex management, mainly in the biological system.

Method modeling is used in specific disciplines, particularly cybernetics, biology, medicine, pedagogy, and sports. All models are categorized according to their model.

The materialistic conceptualization model is used as a tool for organizing categorization, with a focus on deeper knowledge in the recovery of a particular event. [1.422]

Individual models are developed for individual athletes and are based on data from a long study and individual forecasting of the structure of competitive activity and the preparedness of an individual athlete, his reaction to loads, etc. As a result, a variety of individual models of competitive activity, various aspects of fitness, training models, microcycles are obtained, direct preparation for competitions, etc. In sports practice, models of all three levels are used. Higher-level models, providing general dispute directions

training and participating in competitions are detailed in individual models and create the prerequisites for the versatile management of training and competitive activities of athletes. In relation to the structure of competitive activity and the preparedness of the main methodology for developing models, along with the study and use of data on groups of highly qualified athletes, comprehensive studies of the makings, abilities, adaptive capabilities, patterns of formation of the main components of sportsmanship, the relationship between individual factors, and the compensatory capabilities of the body of specific athletes should be. It has been established that the effectiveness of using generalized and group models for orienting and correcting the training process is especially high when preparing young or adult athletes who have not reached the top of sportsmanship. As for the training of international-class athletes, the

orientation to such models is not very effective. The fact is that a gifted athlete is, as a rule, a person with pronounced individual traits that can have a variety of manifestations, indicating unique abilities to master sports equipment, the capabilities of various functional systems or the manifestation of volitional qualities, etc. d. [2.603]

1- diagram.

The above questionnaire can be distinguished by the fact that sports modeling is very important. Although little research has been done in this regard, foreign researchers are increasingly learning and promoting modeling techniques for the development of their sports. Reforms in the sport in our country Following the model of sports facilities built in the leading countries of the world, sports facilities are being built in our own country.

Conclusion: The popularization of physical education and sports has led many scholars to analyze the merits of their many different opinions and experiences, suggesting that the modeling approach can be applied at any age and skill level. In physical education and sports, modeling varies by location, time, load, exercise kit, building location, and more. Recognizing the sport as a model,

the methods and techniques that we are constantly using are also a model. Today, we continue to operate in ways that we do not know. At the same time, the development of a single-sport industry is not unique to the modeling approach, and our research has increased the psychological and technical and physical training of young athletes. As a practical recommendation, the use of modeling techniques in the training of young athletes should be thoroughly studied and incorporated into the model taken as a model.

The results of research of the competitive activity of wrestlers give grounds to conclude that the improvement of the quality of technical actions is carried out more efficiently on the basis of the use of a pedagogical model.

Due to the fact that there is a multifactorial nature of the effectiveness of the levels of competitive activity, it is necessary to develop such a pedagogical technology that would represent the content and organization of the training process, taking into account the integral character in competitive activity.

A special aspect of the problem of the formation of the basis of sportsmanship of wrestlers is the development of design and technological activities of an athlete and a team, taking into account modern trends in the development of wrestling.

Any training task in training wrestlers consists of three interrelated parts: organizational, technical-tactical and psychological. The organizational part is the creation and construction in the training process of models of situations of fights, adequate to competitive activity. These conditions include methods of action and norms of movements, competitive space, forms of task performance (individual, group, team).

The technical and tactical part of the task indicates the degree and features of conscious control over the implementation of technical and tactical actions, i.e. explains what the main reference points of the construction and implementation of technical and tactical actions the wrestler should direct their attention to. At the

same time, the main spatio-temporal, quantitative-qualitative and energy parameters of competitive activity are taken into account.

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